

2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone benzoic hydrazone for spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and iron(III) in soil and cement

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2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone benzoic hydrazone (DHBPBH) is employed as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of copper and iron. The reagent forms 1 : 1 greenish yellow coloured complex with copper(II) at pH 4.0 and λ_{\max} 380 nm (ϵ 1.55×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); Sandell's sensitivity 0.004 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, and Beer's law range 0.31–2.2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. It results a brown coloured 2 : 3 complex with iron(III) at pH 5.0 and λ_{\max} 380 nm (ϵ 2.8×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹); Sandell's sensitivity 0.002 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and Beer's law range 0.14–1.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The method has been applied for the determination of copper in soil and alloy samples and iron(III) in cement sample.

Hydrazones are widely used as complexing agents for the spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions¹. In continuation of our work on the use of benzoic hydrazones as analytical reagents for the determination of metal ions², here we report the estimation of copper and iron using 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone benzoic hydrazone (DHBPBH) as analytical reagent.

Results and Discussion

DHBPBH reacts with copper(II) and iron(III) in the pH range 2–7 giving greenish yellow and brown coloured compounds respectively. Both the complexes showed λ_{\max} at 380 nm against reagent blank. The copper complex showed maximum absorbance at pH 4–5 and the iron complex at pH 5.0–5.5. Hence studies were carried out at pH 4.0 for the Cu complex and at pH 5.0 for the Fe complex. A minimum of 20-fold and 15-fold excess of the reagent was necessary to obtain maximum and constant colour development with Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} respectively. Presence of excess reagent did not affect the colour intensity. The formation of the colours was instantaneous on mixing the metal ion with the reagent and the colours being stable for more than 24 h.

It was observed that Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} can be determined in the range 0.31–2.2 and 0.14–1.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of Cu^{II}-DHBPBH complex were found to be 1.55×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.004 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively, and those for Fe^{III}-DHBPBH complex 2.8×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.002 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The detailed statistical analysis was carried out and the results are given in Table 1.

Effect of various diverse species normally associated with copper and iron was studied. Tolerance limits (μg in parenthesis) of various diverse species are as follows : Zn^{II} (200); Mn^{II} (600); W^{VI} (500); Pb^{II} (400); Cr^{VI} and Pd^{II}

(200); Ni^{II} (200); Ag^I (180); Pt^{IV} (160); Hg^{II} (100); Mo^{VI} (60); V^V (30); Ti^{IV} (20); EDTA (1600); S₂O₃²⁻ (550); C₂O₄²⁻ (400); tartrate (400); SCN⁻ (300); I⁻ (280); F⁻ (200); CO₃²⁻ (180); PO₄³⁻ (100). Most of the anions and cations did not interfere in the present method. In the determination of copper, Fe^{III} was masked up to 580 μg by adding 950 μg of citrate. Hence the method for Cu^{II} determination becomes highly selective in presence of citrate.

Table 1. Statistical analysis of determination of copper(II) and iron(III) with 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone benzoic hydrazone

System	y-Intercept	Angular coeff.	Corr. coeff.	Students t value	Variance $\times 10^{-5}$	Detection limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
Cu ^{II} -DHBPBH	0.006	0.24	0.999	3.8	5.5×10^{-5}	0.11
Fe ^{III} -DHBPBH	0.025	0.44	0.999	3.1	5.7×10^{-5}	0.05

The metal-to-reagent ratio in the coloured solutions determined by Job's, mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods, was found to be 1 : 1 and 2 : 3 in Cu^{II}-DHBPBH and Fe^{III}-DHBPBH respectively. The formation constants of the complexes determined by Job's method, was found to be 6×10^4 and 6.1×10^{13} for Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} complex respectively.

The sample solutions of steel, soil and cement were prepared by standard procedures³. The amounts of copper and iron present were determined using the present method. Analysis of steel sample (BAS 179/2, Cu 58.5 and Zn35.8%) gave satisfactory results with an error of ± 0.1 –0.2% and the soil-18 sample (Cu 88.85, Ni 50.5, Co 40.35, Zn 33.33 and Pb 20.2 ppm) analysed gave a relative error of ± 0.9 –3.5%. Analysis of iron present in Portland cement (CaO 50.6, SiO₂ 20.25, MgO 2.3 and Fe₂O₃ 1.2%) gave a relative error of ± 0.25 –3.3%.

The present method is simple, rapid, sensitive, selective and also more sensitive than that reported by Kavlentis⁴ and more selective than that of Berger and Selman⁵ in the determination of copper. In the determination of iron, the present method is more sensitive than that proposed by Nevado *et al.*⁶ and more selective than that proposed by Zater *et al.*⁷.

Experimental

2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone benzoic hydrazone (DHBPBH) (m.p. 274–76°) was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone and benzoic hydrazide in ethanol medium adopting the general procedure. A 0.01 M solution of the reagent in DMF was used in the analytical studies.

Stock solutions of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} were prepared by dissolving the requisite amounts of copper sulphate and ferric nitrate (AnalaR) in distilled water. Few drops of nitric acid was added to the Fe^{III} solution to prevent the turbidity. The metal ions were determined by standard methods⁸. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solutions were employed to maintain the required pH.

The absorption and pH measurements were carried out

on an Elico CL-27 spectrophotometer and Phillips PP 9046 pH meter respectively.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution, buffer solution (5 ml) of appropriate pH and DHBPBH (1×10^{-2} M; 1 ml) were added and made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 380 nm against reagent blank and the amount of the metal ion determined.

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